

Complexometric Determination of Thallium in Isolation, Alloys and Complexes using Thiosulphate as a Selective Masking Agent

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Complexometric methods for determining thallium reported earlier^{1,2} could not be used for its determination in the presence of diverse metal ions because of their interference and poor selectivity. Few reagents have been suggested as releasing agents for the selective decomposition of Tl-EDTA complex. Thiopyrin³, hydrazine sulphate⁴, 3-n-propyl-4-amino-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole⁵, thiosemicarbazide⁶, thiocarbohydrazide⁷ and 2-mercaptoethanol⁸ have been employed for this purpose. Sodium thiosulphate, a simple, cheap and readily available reagent, has potentialities for use as a reducing as well as a complexing agent, and can be used for selective decomposition of Tl-EDTA complex. The present study reports the feasibility of using sodium thiosulphate, which can form a strong complex with thallium. The reagent is found to be a better complexing agent.

Results and Discussion

The quantitative displacement of EDTA from the Tl-EDTA complex by thiosulphate indicates that the Tl-thiosulphate complex is more stable than the Tl-EDTA complex at room temperature and that EDTA is released instantaneously. For the complete release of EDTA, a slight excess of thiosulphate above the molar ratio of 1 : 3 is necessary. It is found that 10 mg of sodium thiosulphate cause immediate release of the EDTA bound to 2 mg of thallium giving a clear solution. There is no change of pH on addition of the releasing agent, so the liberated EDTA can be titrated without adjusting the pH of the solution immediately. The results are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF Tl^{III} IN SOLUTION

Tl taken mg	Tl found ^a mg	Recovery %
2.76	2.76	100.00
6.90	6.89	99.86
13.80	13.78	99.86
27.60	27.54	99.78
41.40	41.36	99.90
50.50	50.49	99.98
60.00	60.01	100.01
70.80	70.77	99.96
75.09	75.05	99.95

Mean of 5 determinations

A number of metal ions and anions were studied for their interference in the determination of thallium by this method. Although thiosulphate is used to mask Cu^{II} in EDTA titrations, it does so only if added before the EDTA, reducing Cu^{II} and forming a stable complex with Cu^I produced⁹. It can not reduce Cu^{II} in the presence of EDTA, since the Cu^{II}-EDTA complex is stronger than the Cu^I-EDTA complex that the conditional redox potential for the Cu^{II}/Cu^I couple is 0.5 V. Sn^{IV}, Zr^{IV}, Pd^{II} and Hg^{II} interfere rather severely, but the interference can be obviated by using suitable secondary masking agents such as fluoride (10% NH₄F, 5–10 ml) for Zr^{IV} (10 mg) and Sn^{IV} (28 mg) and thiocyanate ion (NH₄SCN 10%, 5–10 ml) for Pd^{II} (8 mg) and Hg^{II} (25 mg). The reduction of Au can be prevented by adding NH₄F (5 ml of 10% solution). The results (Table 2) reveal that many cations and anions can be tolerated.

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF Tl^{III} IN PRESENCE OF DIVERSE IONS

Metal ions	Amount of Tl taken = 5.51 mg		Recovery %
	Amount taken mg	Tl found	
Cu ^{II}	25	5.49	99.04
Mn ^{II}	12	5.50	99.82
Zn ^{II}	100	5.50	99.82
Cd ^{II}	64	5.50	99.82
Co ^{II}	30	5.50	99.82
Ni ^{II}	30	5.52	100.18
Al ^{III}	25	5.51	100.00
Fe ^{III}	30	5.51	100.00
Ru ^{III}	8	5.50	99.82
Rh ^{III}	8	5.49	99.64
Au ^{IIIa}	8	5.50	99.82
Pt ^{IV}	12	5.50	99.82
V ^{IV}	10	5.51	100.00
Sn ^{IVa}	25	5.49	99.36
Hg ^{IIa}	25	5.49	99.63
Pd ^{IIb}	8	5.52	100.09
Zr ^{IVa}	10	5.50	99.82
U ^{IV}	10	5.50	99.82
Borate	200	5.50	99.82
Sulphate	200	5.50	99.82
Chloride	200	5.50	99.82
Tartrate	200	5.51	100.00
Acetate	200	5.50	99.82
Fluoride	200	5.52	100.09
Oxalate	200	5.51	100.00

^aMasked by fluoride ion ^bMasked by thiocyanate ion

The results of analyses of alloy and complex samples are presented in Tables 3 and 4.

The proposed method has the following salient features. (i) The reagent is cheap and readily available. (ii) The results are accurate and precise. (iii) The method is simple, rapid as it requires neither heating for quantitative release of EDTA nor any solvent for extraction since the Tl-thiosulphate complex does not precipitate. (iv) The reagent is relatively stable in water in presence of a small amount of chloroform; but in this experiment freshly prepared solutions are used every time. (v) It can also be used for determination of the composition of the alloy solutions containing thallium. (vi) It is successfully used for the characterisation of Tl complexes.

TABLE 3—DETERMINATION OF Tl^{III} IN ARTIFICIAL SOLUTION*

Metal alloy (composition%)	Tl present mg	Tl found mg	Recovery %	Std. deviation
Pb : Tl (80 : 20)	20.00	20.02	100.10	0.02
Hg : Tl (91 : 3 : 8.7)	8.70	8.69 ^a	99.89	0.03
Pb : Sn : Tl (70 : 20 : 10)	10.00	10.02 ^b	100.20	0.03
Pb : Sb : Tl : Sn (72 : 15 : 8 : 5)	8.00	8.01 ^b	100.12	0.04
Au : Ag : Tl (30 : 30 : 40)	40.00	40.01 ^a	100.02	0.02

*Average value of three determinations. ^aHg and Au by thiocyanate ion. ^bSn masked by fluoride ion

TABLE 4—ANALYSIS OF THALLIUM COMPLEXES

Compd.	Tl present mg	Tl [*] found mg
Tl(C ₃ H ₅ N ₄ S) ^a	61.30	61.38
Tl(C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₄ S) ^b	46.51	46.69
Tl(C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₄ S) ^c	46.97	47.08
Tl(C ₂ H ₂ N ₃ S) ^d	60.73	60.64
Tl(C ₃ H ₃ N ₄ OS) ^e	58.83	58.93
Tl(C ₅ H ₉ N ₄ S) ^f	56.52	56.39

*Average value of six determinations. ^aComplex of 4-amino-5-mercapto-3-methyl-1,2,4-triazole. ^bComplex of 3-(*o*-tolylloxymethyl)-4-amino-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole. ^cComplex of 4-benzylidene-3-ethyl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole. ^dComplex of 5-amino-2-mercapto-1,3,4-thiodiazole. ^eComplex of 4-amino-3-mercapto-1,2,4-triazin(4*H*)-5-one. ^fComplex of 4-amino-5-mercapto-3-*n*-propyl-1,2,4-triazole.

The mechanism of the reaction is

The +1 oxidation state of thallium in its complex is further confirmed by spot test¹⁰.

Experimental

Thallium(III) standard solution was prepared using thal- lous nitrate (G.R., E. Merck) according to the reported pro- cedure¹¹ and standardised by the chromat method¹².

EDTA solution (0.02 mol dm⁻³) was prepared by dissolv- ing the disodium salt of EDTA (AnalaR) in distilled water. Zinc sulphate solution (0.02 mol dm⁻³) prepared by dis- solving zinc sulphate (AnalaR) in distilled water, was standardised by the complexometric method¹¹. Sodium thiosulphate 10% solution (AnalaR) was prepared in water and xylenol orange (CDH) 0.5% solution in water.

Procedure : To a solution containing 2.76–75.09 mg of Tl^{III}, 0.02 mol dm⁻³ EDTA solution was added in excess, diluted to about 100 ml and the pH adjusted to 5.0–6.0 with hexamine. The excess of EDTA was then titrated with 0.02 mol dm⁻³ zinc sulphate solution using xylenol orange as in- dicator. Sodium thiosulphate solution in water was then added in excess and left to stand for about 5 min with in- termittent shaking. The EDTA released was then titrated against the zinc sulphate solution to the same end-point, the colour changed from yellow to red as before.

Alloy compositions were prepared by mixing the respective metal ions. The amount of thallium present in the mixture was determined by the recommended proce- dure. The thallium(I) complexes (0.1–0.3 g) were decom- posed using aqua regia and heated to near dryness and the residue was dissolved in water and made up to 100 ml. Ali- quots of 10 ml were used for the determination of Tl^{III} by the proposed procedure.

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